

**The Dark Faces among the Slave Trade.
Mariners of African Origin in Spanish Ships (1817-1845)¹**

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INTRODUCTION

The dynamics generated by the slave trade turned Africans into more than human commodities: it also made them accomplices of the odious trade across the Atlantic. Théodore Canot, a slave-trader based off the coast of Africa in the nineteenth century, wrote that “three quarters of the shipped slaves are the result of wars among the natives, which the Europeans, with their avarice and ambition, have encouraged” (Canot 1976, 77). Although there is a grain of truth in his words, reality was much more complicated. Slavery and slave-trading in the black continent was old: its kingdoms had long provided slaves to Eastern realms, and by the sixteenth century, they had developed sophisticated mechanisms for supplying slaves to ships destined for the New World (see Morgan 2017; Ferreira 2012; Hazel 2011; Pètrè-Grenouilleau 2004; Ewald 1990, 1992; Fage 1981, 1980, 1969, 1959). According to estimates made by the team of researchers behind the Trans-Atlantic slave trade databases, 12,521,335 slaves were shipped between 1501 and 1875, and an estimated 10,187,362 of the slaves disembarked in the Americas did so between 1701 and 1870.²

An ample bibliography confirms that both African and European rulers benefited from the slave trade, and that the forced displacement of this great many human beings was made possible only through their complicity. Although it is not this paper’s object to analyze the participation of African kingdoms in the slave trade, it is worth recalling the role that they played in the capture, sale, and shipment of slaves from the coasts of Africa to the European colonies in the Americas.³ For one thing, paraphrasing H.S. Klein, the slave trade is not only essential to understand slaves’ culture, their ways of living and dying in America, but also those of their descendants more generally (Klein 2008, 135). But more importantly, as this paper shows, the slave trade was a profitable pursuit for many African kingdoms, and this is intricately bound with the paper’s main subject of study. As has already been mentioned, the trade was one of the most important political structures and economic pillars of several African states. The

Dahomey and Asante kingdoms, for instance, collaborated closely with the Europeans in the African West Coast, acting as middlemen in the Atlantic trade.⁴ Several diaries and memoirs kept by slave ship captains and traders in the sixteenth, seventeenth, and eighteenth centuries contain multiple references to the Africans employed by the shipping crews that awaited at the coast to complete their cargo and sail off towards American soil (Rediker 2014; Shumway 2011; Berendt 2010; Snelgrave 2008). Many of the ports' pilots, stevedores, and interpreters were African. Members of the Kru and Fante peoples, coastal groups whose marine and shipping skills were abundant, profited from the trade. Their knowledge of the African coasts gained them employment in the tasks of loading the enslaved, and "as middlemen between the Europeans and the sellers of negroes" (Snelgrave 2008, 168; Hawthorne 2010).

Numerous Africans decided to go on board the slave ships as interpreters or sailors. They added to the heterogeneity of the ships' crews, whose men hailed from different parts of Europe, Africa, Asia, and the Americas. Thus, throughout the 18th century, Asian and African seamen sailed from British, Portuguese, French, and North American ports, often working as cooks, attendants, or cabin boys (Rediker 2014, 253-254).⁵ Nineteenth century crews maintained this diversity, including those under Spanish flags. According to *Voyages: The Trans-Atlantic Slave Trade Database*, Spanish and Portuguese ships ended up controlling more than 80% of the traffic, and their crews included Africans and descendants of slaves born in the Americas. Some of these men held skilled jobs such as carpenters, coopers, and the like.

In any case, the presence of black sailors and hands in Spanish slave ships was commonplace enough to include their mention in the treaty signed between England and Spain forbidding the slave trade. But this common contemporary knowledge stands in contrast to the little attention that the historiography has paid the men of African origin, slave or free, who worked in the ships that traversed the so-called middle passage. It is true that, in comparison to the dimensions reached by the trafficking of African slaves, theirs was a but a small presence. But this is no reason to ignore it. Notwithstanding the moral uneasiness raised by this subject, their presence evidences Africans' capacity to adapt and survive in colonial slave societies, as well as their autonomy and agency to climb the social ladder. L. Nicolau offers a good example by looking at the participation of freedmen in the trade in San Salvador de Bahia (Parés, 2017).

We will address this reality, specifically bringing to the fore the collaboration and participation of seamen of African origin in Spanish slave ships between 1817 and 1845, a period in which 94% of the slaves illegally sent to America went to a Cuban or Brazilian port.⁶ However, since most of the identified men correspond to crews destined to the Caribbean island, Cuba and its surrounding waters and routes feature more largely in our analysis. The years chosen to bracket the period correspond to the year the first Anglo-Spanish Anti-Slave Trade treaty was signed (1817), and the year the Spanish Penal Code included sanctions for the crime of trading in slaves (1845). At this point, it is worth recalling that tracking down documentary evidence of illicit activities is quite difficult. In the case that concerns us, moreover, the scant documentation generated by traders, and the more numerous generated by those who persecuted the trade, pay very little attention to common sailors. Attention was centered on captains or masters, consignees, and shipowners, making it hard to identify and know more about ships' crews. That said, we believe that making the participation of black seamen in Spanish slavers visible and comprehensible through concrete examples, is an important contribution to the historiography of slavery, for it increases our knowledge of the ways in which men of African origin profited from and suffered from the slave trade, particularly in the American colonies.

SEAMEN OF AFRICAN ORIGIN IN THE ANGLO-SPANISH ANTI-SLAVE TRADE TREATIES OF 1817 AND 1835

On the 23rd of September of 1817, Spain and England signed in Madrid a treaty to end the African slave trade. Each government agreed to allow for the capture of any English or Spanish ship with a slave cargo. The very first article in the protocol of instructions given to the warships of both countries specified that, "black sailors or servants found on board would not in any case constitute cause enough for the ship's capture" (Cantillo 1843, 804). The instructions thus confirmed the participation of black seamen in slavers, and addressed the nature of the conditions of their labor: forced, if they were slaves working for their masters, or voluntary, if they were free (or freed) men.

In the case of slaves, the majority of those who were to be found aboard slave ships belonged to the ships' owners and officers, and they were employed as hands, in sailing tasks as well as those related to serving their masters. This was the case with the schooner *Felicidad*. Captured in November of 1834 with 164 slaves on board, one of its

crewmembers was a slave owned by its captain, Francisco Panlevito.⁷ The *Venganza*, captured in 1845, counted four slaves in its crew who, according to the schooner's captain, Mariano Aldecoa, were his personal property.⁸ The presence of slaves in slavers' crews was not an exclusively Spanish practice. In the Portuguese brig *Maria de la Gloria*, captured in 1824 by the Spanish cruiser *Marte* off Havana's Fortress of San Carlos de la Cabaña, three of the five black hands were the personal property of the well-known trader and owner of the ship, José Joaquim de Oliveira, while the other two were free men (according to the brig's officers). The ship had been destined towards Brazil, but after it was captured by the pirate ship *Romano* some forty leagues off the port of Onim, the captain had decided to sail towards Cuba.⁹

Going back to the treaty: its fourth article stated that black seamen "would be considered Spaniards, if they belong as slaves or as subjects to the Spanish Crown; or if they have been freed in the domains of His Catholic Majesty" (Cantillo 1843, 805). In theory, then, they were judged as Spaniards, so that in effect, slave ships erased the legal differences between free or enslaved white, black, and mulatto crewmembers. This is indeed noteworthy, if we keep in mind that a slave, in the words of Arango y Parreño, did not exist in society, in the State, nor in the city (Arango 2005, 357).

The truth of the matter was that the environs in which the trade was carried out, as well as its very nature, made it difficult to determine the origin and the character of the captured sailors who were to be punished for infringing the law. The judges of mixed tribunals found that establishing crewmembers' identity was a real challenge, as the case of Alexander Journée illustrates. This young black man was found aboard the schooner *Santiago* when it was captured in May of 1830, close to the Castillo del Morro in Santiago de Cuba, by the English sloop *Sparrowhawk*. Journée declared that he was a 23-year-old, single, Catholic sailor who had been born in Curazao but resided in Jamaica. He said that the *Santiago* had sailed off its namesake city's port on August of 1829 with a cargo of rum and other goods for Bras, in the African coast. He declared that they had delivered the cargo to the country's king, who had paid for it with 142 slaves.¹⁰ The English commissioners believed that the young man might be a British subject who was lying about his birthplace, and instead of handing him over to Cuba's Captain-General, they request information from the Dutch consul regarding the truth of Journée's Curazao story. The consul refused to answer, replying that he had no instructions from his government on how to act in such a case. Asked how should the

affair proceed, the judge acknowledged that it was practically impossible to ascertain a person's nationality in a case like this, and argued that "some measures must be adopted to prevent, on the one hand, the harm caused by inadequate procedures, and on the other, the more serious harm caused by the increase in criminal acts that could result from impunity".¹¹ Everything indicates that, despite the English commissioners' suspicions, Alexander Journée was not judged as a British subject. According to the sentence dated May 21st, 1830, the ship's entire crew was sent to prison, which means that the young sailor was probably judged as a Spaniard and punished along with the rest of his mates. In a letter dated in September of that same year and addressed to British State Secretary J. Backhouse, Treasury Chambers J. Steward acknowledged that they did not have sufficient evidence to guarantee that the trial would have had the desired results.¹²

Unlike the first treaty, the 1835 agreement did not include references to black mariners in the instructions given to the Spanish and English ships that were meant to halt the traffic. Does this mean that crews no longer included men of African origin? No: it is more likely that the treaty simply ignored their presence by focusing on the officers and the most important crewmembers. For instance, the fourth article of annex B on the Regulation of the Mixed Tribunals specified that "judges, named respectively by each of the two nations, will proceed, first, to examine the documents of the captured vessel, and then, to take the declarations of the master or commander, followed by those of at least two or three of said vessel's most important crewmembers..." (Cantillo 1843, 863). The protagonists of our analysis would seldom be a part of that select group, for the cases that we have found reveal that they were usually engaged in sailing and auxiliary tasks or in service duties.

In sum, the legislation related to this second treaty contributed in making black seamen even more invisible, but there is no reason to assume that they were no longer working in slave ships. As an example, we have the two sailors of African origin on the *General Laborde* schooner, which was captured at the end of 1835 by the English sloop *Champion*. The latter's officers suspected that the schooner had unloaded a slave cargo in southern Cuba, and they pointed at the fact that the schooner was fitted with the irons and appurtenance necessary for transporting slaves. According to Captain Ramón Trillo's declarations, and to the registration officer who signed the vessel's documents in the port of Havana, two black men had sailed from Trinidad as part of the *General*

Laborde's crew: one was a young cabin boy while the other was a cook.¹³ The documents are not very detailed, and they do not specify birthplace, condition, or if the men were kin, but at least they record their presence.

The slave trade, like any other profit-oriented shipping enterprise, filled some agents' coffers (*factors*, shipowners, operators, captains, and pursers) while allowing others to find employment, however risky or violent, as was the case of seamen. Each ship at sea was a universe onto itself, of synchronized and hierarchical cooperation, which included slaves and which was governed by a strict discipline (Linebaugh and Rediker 2005). Such discipline was necessary to overcome the voyages' adversities and risks, and to keep the heterogeneous crews under control. Sailors were often sacrificed in favor of their officers. Although the anti-slave trade legislation punished crewmembers, their punishments were much more lenient than those accorded to officers and shipowners. On many an occasion, consignors protected their captains by registering a given sailor as the ship's master. This practice became more frequent after 1835, when the new legislation centered its sanctions on the captain and main officers. Thus, Portuguese sailor Joaquim da Souza Pinto, of the *Constituçao* schooner, captured in 1838, and Cantabrian Juan Manuel Benzanillas, of the *Columbia* sloop, captured in 1848, declared having been ordered to pretend to be their ships' captains if they were captured by English cruisers. Da Souza appeared as the *Constituçao* master, and the real captain, Malaga-born Juan Batalla, was registered as a passenger, but their true identities were determined at the trial and their punishments were proportional to their positions. Benzanillas was not as fortunate, and he ended up serving the sentence that should have befallen the ship's true captain, Mas Roig (alias El Pigat) (Chaviano forthcoming; Rodrigo 2017, 111-137). This was only one of the innumerable risks faced by seamen engaged in the illegalized slave trade. The pay must have compensated the risks, however, for, according to Thomas, crews of slavers had higher wages than those in other vessels, and it was relatively easy for slavers to find willing seafarers (Thomas 1998, 670).

There is neither documentary evidence of African descents placed in such false positions nor of black seamen at the top of Spanish crews. However, they could lose their freemen status when their ships docked at certain ports. Sharla M. Fett has analyzed the narrow margin between their freedom and slavery at Southern American ports, such as Charleston. There was a remarkable chance of being sold as slaves there.

Her work also refers to the treatment they received when they were retained by the US Navy, especially since 1835. The "recaptives" and released from the trafficking situation, that is, subjected to white control and ownership, was very similar (Sharla 2017, 2010). Therefore, these dangers evinced those sailors' life passed through two parallel realities: one aboard ships at sea and the other outside them at land.

In any case, the limited possibilities they had to promote inside the crew suggest Linebaugh and Rediker's "hierarchy" could not be considered as a compact and homogeneous group in these cases. This was particularly true because the Spanish merchant navy, and also the slave ships, portrayed the guild system of the Spanish society and cities, where freemen or slaves were only allowed to do some specific jobs and tasks (Christopher 2006). Most black crewmembers were assistant cooks, cabin boys, and deckhands, as we saw in the *General Laborde* mentioned above, although some also worked as carpenters, coopers, and at other skilled jobs.

Louis Rolle was one of these men. Described as a "man of color", he was on board the schooner *Nuevo Campeador* when the English frigate *Aurora* on September 29th, 1826 captured his ship off Santiago de Cuba's Castillo del Morro with a cargo of 263 *bozal* slaves. Rolle declared that he was a 26-year-old, single Catholic native of Martinique, and that he worked on board as a carpenter. He admitted that the ship had indeed left "Calabar, on the African coast, with a shipment of 300 or more slaves, of whom 260 or more were still on board upon the ship's capture, for the rest had died during the voyage".¹⁴ The crew was sentenced to prison, and the ship and its cargo were declared a good prize by the Mixed Commission of Havana¹⁵. We do not know how many times Rolle worked as a carpenter in a slave ship, but we can estimate his wages for this particular engagement: given that the voyage lasted nearly four months—the ship had departed Santiago de Cuba on May 30th, 1826, and been captured on September—Rolle would have earned around 120 pesos. This estimate assumes that a carpenter's wages in a slaver in 1826 did not differ much from those in 1829, when a carpenter on board the *Semirámide* schooner earned 30 pesos a month, according to that vessel's records. This was no negligible salary, for it was surpassed only by that of the captain, the first mate, and the boatswain, and was nearly the same as that of the surgeon and the second mate. However, all of these crewmembers and officers earned a bonus for every slave that they delivered, whereas the carpenter earned only his wages (Maluquer 1974, 83-136).

No records have been found to indicate that skin color determined crewmembers' wages. Instead, it seems that each job was compensated according to the responsibility and skill that it demanded. The multiple testimonies included by Rediker suggesting that skin color bore little significance in the English slave ship crews that operated in the eighteenth century seem applicable in the period and cases under study, albeit for different reasons. Rediker concluded that "the privileges attached to white skin could be reverted, even on voyages to the Americas, when at the end of the journey they became superfluous, disposable laborers" (Rediker 2014, 283). During the period that we are addressing, the trade was prosecuted as illegal, so that the need for vigilance given the menace of capture by the English navy, meant that all men were engaged in work and that the risks associated with the trade were much higher. Therefore, the value of both the cargo and the work involved in transporting it, increased accordingly.

However, racial discrimination was evident in the glass ceiling that kept black sailors from rising up the ranks. As we have mentioned above, Spanish prosecutors granted considerable significance to the position held by each crewmember as well as his place of origin. It was therefore understandable when seamen of African descent did not always feature in the documents generated by the capture of slavers, given the relative pettiness of their employments. It seems that only when there were doubts regarding the identity of a specific mariner, did the identification of others, including black sailors, make it into the documents. Such doubts existed in the case of the *Midas* brig, whose crew was taken in Havana in 1829. According to the log, there were five English crewmembers, but four of them had apparently given false names. The fifth was the cook's assistant, Francis Jozé. Although the color of his skin is not specified, he was probably a black man. Hailing from Jamaica, he had embarked in Havana on a voyage to the African island of Sao Tomé with four other English seafarers. In his case, the commissioners were able to certify his name and birthplace, and he was repatriated to Jamaica to be judged there.¹⁶

William Murray was another English subject of African descent. Aboard the brig *Emilio* (alias *Cesar*) when it was captured in 1830 by the British sloop *Victor*, he was the only member of the crew not detained in Havana. Not only was he a British subject, born in Bermuda, he was also, according to his declaration, innocent from having partaken in the slave trade, for when he found out that the ship was a slaver, he had deserted. If he was still on board upon the ship's capture, it was only because he had not been allowed

to leave and was forced to remain without pay.¹⁷ Murray was indeed not included in the crew log, but no other crewmember confirmed his version in their declarations. His story might have been false, but the commission believed it to be true, for its members knew that in their efforts to secure crews, ship captains were not always honest about the kind of cargo that they would be transporting (Thomas 1998, 489; Rediker 2014, 250). It is also true that sailors often pleaded ignorance to save themselves from punishment, as the documents generated by the trade's persecution reveal. This strategy complemented the also common subterfuge of providing false names and/or birthplaces in the crew lists or rolls, as the above-mentioned English sailors of the *Midas*, where English sailors were registered with Spanish names.¹⁸ Sometimes, seamen would give their real names, but in another language. This is what commissioner Macleay suggested to commissioner Aberdeen may have happened in William Murray's case: he might have inscribed a fake, Spanish version of his name in the log, and then lied about his desertion.¹⁹ Any trick or ploy was useful to avoid capture or sentencing, particularly in the case of the English, whose Parliament had declared the slave trade an act of piracy since 1824 and dealt harsher sentences. Precisely because it was an illegal activity, slavers' crews were often comprised of men who lived on the fringes of society, and for whom lying would have constituted the least of their sins.

In any case, a ship was a space that Linebaugh and Rediker described as a universe characterized by *sui generis* relations, thanks in part to the fact that its crew could be comprised of men hired from all the corners of the world (Linebaugh and Rediker 2005, 176). Spanish slave ships also partook of this global character. Moreover, the capacity to hire men from any port made it hard to identify the true origins of their crews, for even though the ships were Spanish, they sailed from ports that were more often than not in non-Spanish territories. According to their own declarations, black crewmembers hailed from English, Dutch, and French Caribbean colonies. Does this mean that no men of African descent born in Spanish territories worked in Spanish crews? This seems highly unlikely. The cook and the cabin boy found aboard the *General Laborde* were probably of African descent, and although the documentation makes no explicit reference to their origin, it specifies that they both spoke Spanish, and that their names were included in the crew list. The first was called Francisco Alvarez and was probably Hispanic; it has been impossible to determine the identity of the second.

But everything indicates that the number of seafarers of African descent born in Spanish colonies and enrolled in Spanish and perhaps Portuguese slave ships, was probably small when compared to the number of black crewmembers from English, Dutch and French territories enrolled in those same ships. We do not know up to what degree the legality of slavery in each domain influenced this participation. However, there is a clear relationship between the dates of illegalization of the trade—in England in 1807, the Netherlands in 1814, and France in 1815—and the increasing participation of Spanish ships in the trade. Despite its illegality, African slaves made their way into the English, French, and Dutch colonies in the Caribbean, but it was the Portuguese and Spanish colonies across the Americas which became the hegemonic destinies for these human cargoes, and this might have influenced the displacement of the slave ship crews' origins. According to the cited Trans-Atlantic Slave Trade Database, nearly 67% of slaves disembarked in continental and insular America between 1821 and 1870 were transported from Africa in Portuguese ships; 26% were transported in Spanish ships; 6.4% in French ships; 0.12% in US ships, and 0.02% in Dutch ships.²⁰

Another possible explanation for the small number of black seafarers of Hispanic origin is that the heyday of the plantation economy in Spain's overseas territories—by then reduced to Puerto Rico, Cuba, and the Philippines—meant that the majority of the free blacks and mulattos in the Caribbean colonies was engaged in the sugar fields and centrals. We should also keep in mind the geography of the region. The islands were all relatively close to one another, and it was not hard for men of the Dutch, French or English colonies to find their way to Cuba or to Spanish ships. Cuba was the Caribbean's the main reception center of enslaved Africans: approximately 87% of all slaves sent to the Caribbean between 1811 and 1870 were destined for Cuba, but other islands were often used as ports of call in slaving voyages to and from Africa.²¹ For, although the trade was illegal in these places, islands such as Saint Thomas, Santa Cruz or Saint Barthelemy served as ports of call in which ships could find foodstuffs and provisions, as well as crewmembers.

INTERPRETERS, SLAVE-DRIVERS AND FACTORS

Spanish ships also counted African men from coastal peoples such as the Kru in their crews. These were the “Atlantic creoles” (Berlin 1996, 251-288), free West African men who acted as middlemen and collaborators in the slave trade. They were not

Spanish subjects, and therefore, the 1817 and 1835 treaties did not refer to them, even though their presence aboard Spanish slave ships was not uncommon. This is evidenced in the correspondence sent by the British commissioner of Sierra Leone to secretary Canning in June of 1824 regarding the schooner *Conchita*, captured off the coast of Africa. The commissioners made specific mention of the Africans that British mariners saw jumping off the *Conchita* upon their approach. They believed these were men from the Calabar river who had helped conceal the schooner to avoid detection by the English cruisers.²² Schooner *Atafa Primo*, captained by Spaniard José Maury in 1830, also had free African men aboard—six, to be exact. Maury was taken before the mixed commission of Sierra Leone, suspected of trading in slaves, but these men stated that they were on the ship of their own free will, and the case was dropped.²³

However, it was their work as interpreters, thanks to their knowledge of English, French, Spanish, and Portuguese as well as of local languages, that made numerous Africans authentic brokers in the reproduction of the *middle passage*. W. Snelgrave, captain of a slave ship in Dahomey during the first half of the eighteenth century, lauded these men's honesty as one of their great qualities, a useful virtue when rebellious or mutinous sentiments threatened peace on board. He described them as “free men natives of the country”, whose services he hired “because they spoke English well” (Snelgrave 2008, 168).²⁴ His journal shows that interpreters not only translated from one language to another: they also worked as brokers and, in some cases, carried out labors of restraint. Théodore Canot's memoir also highlighted the valuable contribution made by interpreters to the slave trade in the nineteenth century. He lamented having “abandoned Whydah on my return trip, without interpreters to help us understand our slaves” which suggests that interpreters' presence aboard slavers was quite common (Canot 1976, 145). Canot was convinced that interpreters would have been able to prevent the revolt that took place on the *Estrella*, clearly referring to interpreter's importance in the trade.

Interpreters' activities are also mentioned in the archives of the British Foreign Office, specifically in the documentation generated by the capture of the schooner *Preciosa* in 1863 off the coast of Havana. According to its captain's declarations, five of the African men found on board were Kru who had been “hired as sailors and interpreters for a salary of 12 dollars a month until their return to their country”. Four others were identified as paid servants hired by three passengers, with wages that ranged from 2 to 4 dollars a month. The British authorities did not find any documents that confirmed the

captain's declaration regarding these supposed contracts. However, it seemed clear that they were not simply *bozales*, for one of the Krumen retracted his previous declaration and confessed that his name was Alessandro, or Lessander; that he spoke French, Spanish, and English; and that he had been on another ship under similar conditions between Matanzas and the Pongo River. Commissioner Schenley wrote that this man's work on the *Preciosa* was key, for "the other Krumen seemed to be under his control, and evidently he was the best man on board at taking care of the unhappy creatures that constituted its cargo".²⁵ Both the commissioner's words and the interpreter's declaration reveal that these men were very perceptive, and that they were fully aware that they were taking part in an illicit activity. This made them very cautious in their declarations—although "uncertainty and fear regarding their future destiny" might also have played a role in their reticence to reveal all that they knew or were.²⁶ But unlike the seafarers of African descent born in the colonies, African interpreters were usually repatriated to Africa, unsentenced—which is what happened to the hired African men of the *Preciosa*.

It is worth recalling that both the *Atafa Primo* and the *Preciosa* had six Kru mariners on board. This seems to suggest that, not only was it habitual for such men to be present in the voyages, but that the number of them included on board corresponded to the number of slaves being transported, which would confirm that they were also paid to "contain" the captives.

They assumed also a contention role together with the English Navy and mixed courts, although this time it was to repress the illegal slave trade. According to D. T. Graden, naval officers and mixed tribunals obtained valuable information through the interviews with slaves found aboard on captured ships, who give them details about their expeditions and their crews (Grade 2011, 393-419). These interrogations are opposed to our analysis subject, but they show the important role of African interpreters and translators in the slave trade.

Although the protagonists of our analysis are mariners, particularly those born in the American colonies, a look at mulatto owners of slave-trading posts in the African coasts is also relevant. There is an ample bibliography on the role played by slave factors (Thornton and Heywood 2009, 86-111; Mouser 2013; Rogers 1940; Knör 2016; Nerin 2015), but we will address only those of mixed European-African parentage who had

some sort of presence as “passengers” in Spanish slavers. After all, “miscegenation” had played a significant role in the construction of the transnational networks that formed the basis of the Atlantic slave trade.

John Ormond and Francisco Felix Da Souza are among the most well-known mongos or *lançados* of the African coast—thanks mostly to Théodore Canot’s memoir. Like many other men in their position, they were the offspring of European traders and the daughters of local chiefs.²⁷ However, they were not the only ones, because there were others less known. For instance, Francisco Zangroniz, who was born into one of the most transnational Spanish families, followed his father’s example and established a factory in Dahomey in association with a reputed slave trader (Barcia, 2016, 303-324). Another, lesser known case, was that of Mr. Curtis, a passenger of the *Preciosa* when this schooner was captured in 1836 by the British, with 285 slaves on board. Curtis was described in the documents as “a tall mulatto, well-built, slightly marked, who speaks English very well, but with an American accent”.²⁸ He declared to be from the Pongo River, where he owned a trading post, and he explained and that he was on the schooner on his way to the United States, for business purposes, and to recover two children who had been sold as slaves.²⁹ It seems that Curtis was no stranger to the British Commissioners of Sierra Leone, for in correspondence dated 1835 they had already identified him and his family as slave-traders based in the Pongo River, with commercial interests and ties in the United States.³⁰

Another of the passengers in this same schooner was a mulatto boy, of approximately 14 years of age, whose name was John Ormond: the son of the notorious slave trafficker, who had passed away in 1833. His mother had placed him under the care of the ship’s captain, Santiago Comas, who was to take him to Cuba to be educated in Matanzas, for “he possessed great wealth, in money, lands, and slaves, in the Pongo River”.³¹ Why Matanzas? It was not uncommon for the children and relatives of the most successful traders to be educated in schools in London, Liverpool, Freetown, Havana, Matanzas, or Charleston. It made sense for Ormond’s heir to become familiar with the language and customs of the Cuban slave market, where most of his cargo was purchased (Mouser 2016, 28). The choice of Captain also confirms the ties between these two shores: of Catalan origin, Santiago Comas was an experienced slave trafficker with ties to dealers such as Pedro Blanco and Pedro Martinez, whose commercial interests extended from the island to Africa and Spain. Captain Comas declared that he

was born in Nueva Barcelona; he also confessed that the slaves on his ship had come from Ormond's widow's trading post.³² He was not the only Comas family member associated with the slave trade in Cuba. M. Zeuske mentioned a Pedro Comas—very likely a relative—who operated in the port of Nuevitas, in northeastern Cuba, which was associated with the slave trade, and was “very close to La Guanaja, Ramón Ferrer's private port” (Zeuske 2017, 81).

The transnational character of these individuals was on par with slave ships' global character, not only because of the composition of the crews, but also because of their role in the web of relations that tied coastal areas around the world through constant and diverse interactions that were based on personal and commercial interests. Take the strategic marriages that produced interracial offspring, such as Curtis, mixing the personal, the transnational, and the economic; or the desire to provide one's mestizo children with a specialized education that allowed them to maintain and improve business, such as Ormond Jr.'s case. The two faces of the same activity, that is, the supply and demand sides of the slave trade, were intertwined in personal, familiar webs, as another case, that of young Singa, shows. The son of Mangobo Fernando, local Congolese king, he was entrusted by his father in 1857 to Captain Manuel Martínez, to be taken to Havana—he paid for this service with several slaves. According to the declarations given by two of these slaves after the ship was captured by an English cruise, Singa was employed as the captain's personal assistant during the voyage.³³

Before concluding, there is another group whose role in the slave trade in Cuba makes them worth mentioning here, even though they were not seafaring folk: the free black men born in Africa or the colonies who assisted in the introduction of the illegally trafficked slaves in the country. When the schooner *Segunda Socorro* was captured off the Cuban coast in 1833 with 307 bozal slaves on board, its captain, José Inzá, declared that the consignees were two mulato men named Faita Antonio, of Bahia de Cochino, and Faita Fajardo, of San Antonio (in central and western Cuba, respectively).³⁴ These men were identified in the documents as “Spaniards who are in the business of mediating”, which means that this was not the only disembarking of slaves that they had facilitated.

Finally, there is the case of Savage, a freedman who worked as an agent in Sierra Leone, for Pedro Blanco, the most well-known Spanish slave trader. In 1835, Savage

bought the brig *Scorpio*, selling it later it to a Spanish captain surnamed Salgado who took it directly to Gallinas to load it with slaves. Since then, and until he was condemned in 1839, the *Scorpio* had voyaged five times to slave outposts across the coasts of Africa (Arnalte 2002). Not many details have been recorded in documents, but the fact that a former slave worked in the slave trade confirms the hypothesis that Africans and Afro-descendants found a livelihood in the slave trade, one that sometimes allowed them to climb up the social ladder.

CONCLUSIONS

The examples described above contribute to clarifying the role played in the slave trade by a minor sector: the seafarers of African origin who worked in the middle passage aboard Spanish slave ships destined for Cuba. Because, notwithstanding their small numbers, they were participants who have been passed over in the historiography, and in order to construct a more complete and accurate understanding of the trade, no contribution is insignificant. The paper has addressed, specifically, those men of African descent, born in Africa or the American colonies, who found their livelihoods in the slave trade, working as cooks or servants in slave ships, or as full-fledged crew members, as carpenters, coopers, hands, and cabin boys. Some factors and agents who facilitated slaves' introduction in Cuba were also men of African descent. All participated in an activity that, we believe speaks not only to and about the cultures of slaves and their descendants, but also of slavery itself, and the livelihood and ways of life that it entailed.

The protagonists of our analysis, born in Martinique, Bermuda, Curacao, Cuba, or Africa itself, knew slavery well—too well, in the case of former slaves. But the fact of their African origin did not stop them from sharing risks and labors as sailors in slave ships dedicated to the trade, even when it was declared illegal. Their presence in the ships was as necessary as it was known, but it is nearly invisible in the historical records because their skin-color prevented them from ever becoming slave ship officers.

REFERENCES

- Arango y Parreño, Francisco de. *Obras*. 2005. Havana. Imagen Contemporánea. Vol. 2.
- Arnalte Barrera, L. Arturo. 2002. *El Tribunal mixto anglo-español de Sierra Leona (1819-1874)*, Ph. D. dissertation, Madrid. ISBN: 978-84-8466-009-5.

- Austen, Ralph A. 1992. "The Mediterranean Islamic Slave Trade Out of Africa: a Tentative Census" in E. Savage (ed.), *The Human Commodity. Perspectives on the Trans-Saharan Slave Trade*, Special Issue, *Slavery and Abolition*. 13 (1): 214-248.
- Barcia, M. 2016. 'Fully Capable of any Iniquity': The Atlantic Human Trafficking Network of the Zangroniz Family, *The Americas* 73:3/July, 303–324.
- Becker, Charles and Martin, Victor. 1975. "Kayor et Boal: Royaumes sénégalais et traite des esclaves au XVIII^e siècle" in *Revue Française d'histoire d'outre-Mer*. t. LXII. Num. 226-227.
- Berendt, Stephen D., Latham, A.J.H. and Northrup David (eds.). 2010. *The Diary of Antera Duke, an Eighteenth- Century African Slave Trade*, Oxford University Press.
- Berlin, Ira. 1996. "From Creole to African: Atlantic Creoles and the Origins of African-American Society in Mainland North America", *William and Mary Quarterly* 53: 251-88.
- Canot, Théodore. 1976. *Memorias de un tratante de esclavos*, Buenos Aires: Centro Editor de América Latina.
- Cantillo, Alejandro del. 1843. *Tratados, convenios y declaraciones de paz y de comercio que han hecho con las potencias extranjeras los monarcas españoles de la Casa de Borbón desde el año de 1700 hasta el día*. Madrid. Imprenta de Alegría y Charlain.
- Chaviano Pérez, Lizbeth. "Malagueños en la trata negrera" in *Política y sociedad en el Mediterráneo. Imágenes de conflictos seculares* (forthcoming)
- Christopher, Emma. 2006. *Slave Ship Sailors and their Captive Cargoes, 1730-1807*. Cambridge University Press.
- Dorigny, Marcel and Gainot, Bernard. 2016. *La Schiavitù in 100 Mappe*. Leg Edizioni SLR, Gorizia.
- Ewald, Janet J. 1990. *Traders and Slaves: State Formation and Economic Transformation in the Greater Nile Valley, 1700-1885*. Madison, University of Wisconsin Press.
- Ewald, Janet J. 1992. "Slavery in Africa and the Slave Trades from Africa". *American Historical Review*. April: 465-485.
- Fage, John Donnelly et S. Mintz (éd.). 1981. *Esclave = facteur de production*, Paris: Dunod.
- Fage, John Donnelly. 1959. *A History of West Africa*. Cambridge University Press.
- Fage, John Donnelly. 1969. "Traite et esclavage dans le contexte historique de l'Afrique occidentale", dans *Journal of African History*, 3: 393-404.
- Fage, John Donnelly. 1980. "Slave and Society in Western Africa c. 1445- c. 1700", *Journal of African History*, 21: 289-310.
- Ferreira, Roquinaldo. 2003. *Transforming Atlantic Slaving: Trade, Warfare and Territorial Control in Angola, 1650-1800*, Los Angeles, University of California.
- Ferreira, Roquinaldo. 2012. *Cross-Cultural Exchange in the Atlantic World: Angola and Brazil during the Era of the Slave Trade*. Cambridge University Press.

- Gordon, David M. 2009. "The Abolition of the Slave Trade and the Transformation of the South-Central African Interior during the Nineteenth Century in *William and Mary Quarterly, Abolishing the Slave Trades*, Series 3. Vol. 66. Num. 4: 915-938.
- Grade, Dale Torston. 2011. "Interpreters, Translators, and Spoken Word in the Nineteenth-Century Transatlantic Slave Trade to Brazil and Cuba", *Ethnohistory*, 58:3, 393-419.
- Harris, John H. 1912. *Dawn in Darkest Africa*. Smith, Elder & Co. London.
- Hawthorne, Walter. 2010. *From Africa to Brazil: Culture, Identity, and an Atlantic Slave Trade, 1600-1830*, Cambridge University Press.
- Hazel, Alastair. 2011. *The last Slave Market*, Constable, London.
- J. Bazán and E. Terray (dir.). 1982. *Guerres de linages et guerres d'États en Afrique*. Paris, Éditions des Archives Contemporaines.
- Klein, H.S. and Vinson, Ben. 2008. *La esclavitud africana en América Latina y el Caribe*. Lima Instituto de Estudios Peruanos.
- Klein, Martin A. 2001. "The Slave Trade and Decentralized Societies" in *The Journal of African History*. Vol. 42, Num. 1: 49-65.
- Knör, Jacqueline and Kohl, Christoph (ed.). 2016. *The Upper Guinea Coast in Global Perspective*. Berghahn. NY. Oxford.
- Linebaugh, Peter and Rediker, Marcus. 2005. *La Hidra de la revolución, Marineros, esclavos y campesinos en la historia oculta del Atlántico*. Barcelona, Crítica.
- Maluquer de Motes, Jordi. 1974. "La burguesía catalana i l'esclavitud colonial: Modes de producció i pràctica política" in *Recerques: Història, economia, cultura*. Num. 3: 83-136.
- Manning, Patrick (ed.). 1996. *Slave Trades, 1500-1800. Globalisation of Forced Labour*. Variorum [Ashgate].
- Morgan, Kenneth. 2017. *Cuatro siglos de esclavitud trasatlántica*. Barcelona, Crítica.
- Mouser, Bruce L. 2013. *American Colony on the Rio Pongo: The War of 1812, the Slave Trade, and the Proposed Settlement of African Americans, 1810-1830*. Africa World Press. Trenton, NJ.
- Mouser, Bruce L. 2016. "Towards a Definition of Transnational as a Family Construct. A Historical and Micro Perspective, in *The Upper Guinea Coast in Global Perspective*. Jacqueline Knör and Christoph Kohl (ed.) Berghahn. NY. Oxford, 30-39.
- Nerin, Gustao. 2015. *Traficants d'ánimes. Els negrers espanyols a l'Àfrica*. Barcelona, Pòrtic.
- Parés, Luis Nicolau. 2017. "Entre Bahia e a Costa da Mina, libertos africanos no tráfico ilegal", in *Salvador da Bahia. Interações entre América e África (séculos XVI-XIX)*. Giuseppina Raggi, João Figueirôa-Rego and Roberta Stumpf (eds). Editora da Universidade Federal da Bahia.
- Pètrè-Grenouilleau, Olivier. 2004. *Les Traits Nègrières*. France: Gallimard.
- Polanyi, Karl. 1965. *Dahomey and the Slave Trade*. Seattle, University of Washington Press.

- Rediker, Marcus. 2014. *El barco de esclavos, una historia humana*. Havana, Imagen Contemporánea.
- Rodney, Walter. 1980. "Slaves and Society in Western Africa, c. 1445-c. 1700". *Journal of African History*, 21.
- Rodrigo y Alharilla, Martin. 2017. "Víctimas y verdugos a la vez: los marineros españoles de la trata ilegal (1845-1866) in *Drassana*, Num. 25: 111-132.
- Rogers, Joel A. 1940. *Your History: From the beginning of Time to the Present*. Pittsburgh Courier Publishing Co.
- Ross, D. 1987. "The Dahomean Middleman System, 1727-c. 1818". *Journal of African History*. 28
- Schafer, Daniel L. 2003. "Family Ties that Bind: Anglo-African Slave Traders in Africa and Florida, John Fraser and His Descendants" in *The Slavery Reader*, Gad Heuman and James Walvin (ed.), Routledge, London, 778-796
- Sharla M. Fett. 2010. "Middle Passages and Forced Migrations: Liberated Africans in Nineteenth-Century US Camps and Ships" in *Slavery and Abolition*, Vol. 31, Num. 1: 75-98, March.
- Sharla M. Fett. 2017. *Recaptured Africans: Surviving Slaves Ships, Detention and Dislocation in the Final Years of the Slave Trade*. University of Carolina Press
- Shumway, Rebecca. 2011. *The Fante and the Transatlantic Slave Trade*. University of Rochester Press. Rochester. NY.
- Snelgrave, W. 2008. *Capitaine William Snelgrave, Journal d'un négrier au XVIIIe siècle*. Paris. Gallimard. Original edition. *A New Account of Some Parts of Guinea, and the Slave-Trade*. James, John and Paul Knapton, London, 1734.
- Thomas, H. 1998. *La trata de esclavos. Historia del tráfico de seres humanos de 1440 a 1870*. Planeta, Barcelona.
- Thornton, John and Heywood, Linda. 2009. "Kongo and Dahomey, 1660-1815: African Political Leadership in the Era of the Slave Trade and Its Impact on the Formation of African Identity in Brazil" in Bernard Bailyn (ed.) *Soundings in Atlantic History: Latent Structures and Intellectual Currents, 1500-1825*. Harvard University Press. Cambridge (MA), 86-111
- Thornton, John K. 1992. *Africa and Africans in the Making of the Atlantic World, 1400-1680*. Cambridge University Press.
- Thornton, John K. 1999. *Warfare in Atlantic Africa, 1500-1800*. Taylor and Francis.
- Trans-Atlantic Slave Trade Database, 2019. *Voyages: The Trans-Atlantic Slave Trade Database*. <https://www.slavevoyages.org/voyage/database> (accessed March 2, 2019).
- Wilks, Ivor. 1975. *Asante in the Nineteenth Century. The Structure and Evolution of a Political Order*. Cambridge University Press.
- Zeuske, Michael. 2017. "Capitanes y comerciantes catalanes de esclavos" in *Negreros y esclavos. Barcelona y la esclavitud atlántica (siglos XVI-XIX)*. Martin Rodrigo and Lizbeth Chaviano (eds.). Barcelona, Icaria.

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² Trans-Atlantic Slave Trade Database, 2019. *Voyages: The Trans-Atlantic Slave Trade Database*. <https://www.slavevoyages.org/voyage/database> (accessed March 2, 2019).

³ For more on slavery and the slave trade in Africa, see Gordon (2009), Hawthorne (2010), Ferreira (2003), Klein (2001), Thornton (1999, 1992), Manning (1996), Ewald (1992), Austen (1992), Bazán and Terray (1980), Rodney (1980), Harris (1912).

⁴ In the 18th century, war between the Akan and Asante generated a large number of captives that were sold to Muslim traffickers located at the north of the Gold Coast as well as to slave ships with a transatlantic destiny. See Morgan (2017), Dorigni and Gainot (2016), Ross (1987), Becker and Martin (1975), Wilks (1975), Polanyi (1965), among others.

⁵ In his book *El barco de esclavos. Una historia humana*, Rediker shows the heterogeneity of crews in English ships, such as the *Bruce Grove* and the *Tartar*, whose cooks were black. The *Tartar*'s cook had been born in the Pongo River. Rediker also confirms the presence of a freedman from Saint Domingue who worked onboard as a cooper.

⁶ Trans-Atlantic Slave Trade Database, 2019. *Voyages: The Trans-Atlantic Slave Trade Database*. <https://www.slavevoyages.org/voyage/database> (accessed March 2, 2019).

⁷ HCPP, Slave Trade, Class A 1834, Num. 46; HCPP, Slave Trade, Class A 1836, Enclosure in Num. 46.

⁸ HCPP, Slave Trade, Class A 1845, Enclosure in Num. 107. It seems that, notwithstanding an old Portuguese passport found among the ship's documents, the ship was Spanish, for not only were its captain and its crew Spanish, but so was the flag that was found on board.

⁹ HCPP, Slave Trade, Class A 1825, Thirty fourth Enclosure in Num. 73.

¹⁰ HCPP, Slave Trade, Class A 1830, Fourth Enclosure in Num. 84.

¹¹ HCPP, Slave Trade, Class A 1830, Enclosure in Num. 100.

¹² “quoted text” (Enclosure in Num. 100)

¹³ HCPP, Slave Trade, Class A 1835, Eighth Enclosure in Num. 142.

¹⁴ HCPP, Slave Trade, Class A 1826-27, Fourth Enclosure in Num. 90.

¹⁵ “quoted text”. If a ship was declared a “good prize”, it was either sold in its entirety or dismantled and sold in parts, and the slaves it carried as cargo were freed.

¹⁶ HCPP, Slave Trade, Class A 1830, Num. 77.

¹⁷ HCPP, Slave Trade, Class A 1830, Enclosure in Num. 109.

¹⁸ Alexander Martínez, Andrés Calle, Juan Mott and Juan Pacad had declared to be from Baltimore, New York, and Ireland (2). The commissioners suspected that their names were false, for none of them were English. HCPP, Slave Trade, Class A 1830, Num. 77.

¹⁹ HCPP, Slave Trade, Class A 1830, Num. 94.

²⁰ Trans-Atlantic Slave Trade Database, 2019. *Voyages: The Trans-Atlantic Slave Trade Database*. <https://www.slavevoyages.org/voyage/database> (accessed March 2, 2019).

²¹ Trans-Atlantic Slave Trade Database, 2019. *Voyages: The Trans-Atlantic Slave Trade Database*. <https://www.slavevoyages.org/voyage/database> (accessed March 2, 2019).

²² HCPP, Slave Trade, Class A 1824-1825, Num. 33.

²³ HCPP, Slave Trade, Class A 1831, Enclosure in Num. 10.

²⁴ Snelgrave described how some of the chiefs held as slaves in his boat tried to convince the interpreter to cut the vessel's moorings while the crew slept, so that the boat would be pushed ashore, and they would recover their freedom. The interpreter revealed the plot to the captain and warned him to watch the slaves closely. Moreover, he told the men that “even if they made it back to land, they should have no doubt that they would be caught again and sold to other ships, so that their plan was for naught”.

²⁵ HCPP, Slave Trade, Class A 1836, Fifth Enclosure in Num. 125.

²⁶ HCPP, Slave Trade, Class A 1836 “quoted text”.

²⁷ In his memoir, Canot speaks of John Ormond, nicknamed Mongo John, as his mentor. The son of a wealthy British slave-trader and a daughter of a chief of the Pongo River area, John was educated in England, and, after his father's death, he spent five years in the British merchant marine. Returning to Africa, he took possession of his inheritance, and continued with the trade. He passed away in 1833. De Souza, known as Cha Cha, was apparently a mulato from Rio de Janeiro. Although it was not known how he had arrived at Africa, he had probably done so as a crewmember in a slaver, and then jumped ship. He had “gone native” so successfully, that he became the Dahomey king's favorite, and held a privileged position as intermediary vis-à-vis the white slave traders, through whom he sent large shipments of slaves to Brazil and Cuba. He died in May of 1849, 143-144.

²⁸ HCPP, Slave Trade, Class A 1836, Fifth Enclosure in Num. 125. It is very likely that this was Thomas Gaffery Curtis, a New England slave trader who had been educated in Liverpool. His father was

Benjamin Curtis, a slave-trader who had arrived at the Pongo River in 1794 from Boston, and his mother was a local woman. (Schafer, 2003, 778-796; Mouser 2016, 30-39).

²⁹ HCPP, Slave Trade, Class A 1836, Fifth Enclosure in Num. 125.

³⁰ HCPP, Slave Trade, Class A 1835, Second Enclosure in Num. 2.

³¹ HCPP, Slave Trade, Class A 1835 “quoted text”. See (Mouser 2016, 26).

³² HCPP, Slave Trade, Class A 1836, Num. 123.

³³ Archivo Nacional de Cuba (ANC), Miscelánea de Expedientes, Legajo 340A, in (Martin 2017).

³⁴ HCPP, Slave Trade, Class A 1833, Enclosure in Num. 18.